

Title: Protocol for a systematic review on cooking skills and food sustainability

Description: To review and synthesize existing research on the association between cooking skills and food sustainability, into Planetary Health and One Health.

For the systematic review of the available evidence, the project will employ a systematic methodology, including extensive literature searches of quantitative and qualitative studies and systematic data extraction following standard methodology.

A combination of search strategies will be employed, including in-depth searches of electronic databases (PubMed, EMBASE, Scopus) using MeSH and free text keywords, searching names of key authors and articles listed as 'related' in PubMed, and searching the references in relevant publications. Inclusion criteria will include peer-reviewed articles, studies involving adults, and research focusing on cooking skills and food sustainability. Key data such as study design, sample size, population characteristics, measures of cooking skills, and food sustainability practices will be extracted. Thematic synthesis and narrative analysis will be conducted to identify patterns, key themes, and gaps in the literature.

Search Strategies:

- Use of MeSH (Medical Subject Headings) terms and free-text keywords.
- Inclusion of synonyms and variations of key terms like "cooking skills," "food sustainability,"
- Manual searches of articles listed as "related" in PubMed.
- Searching references of relevant articles for additional sources.
- Screening the works of key authors identified during the search.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Peer-reviewed publications.
- Studies involving adult populations (≥ 18 years).
- Studies focusing on:
 - Cooking skills: self-reported or objectively assessed.
 - Food sustainability practices: self-reported or objectively assessed
- Quantitative and qualitative studies

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies on subjects < 18 years
- Non-peer-reviewed articles.
- Non-English studies (unless translated)

Sampling Procedure

- Screening: Titles/abstracts first, followed by full-text screening using eligibility criteria
- Data Extraction: Conducted by two reviewers with reconciliation of discrepancies

Sample Characteristics

- Population Characteristics: Studies will include adults from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds and various health conditions, covering multiple geographic regions.

Key Data Extraction Fields

- Study details (author, year, country).
- Population demographics (sample size, age, gender).
- Study design and methods.
- Measures of cooking skills, food sustainability, and diet quality

Analysis Approach

- Quantitative Studies: Descriptive summaries or statistical pooling if data allows.

Data will be extracted by two independent reviewers. Data extraction will be performed using a predefined and pre-tested excel spreadsheet. Study quality will be assessed with appropriate tools, such as the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale.

This systematic review will focus on identifying and analyzing outcomes relevant to the intersection of cooking skills, and food sustainability. Key outcomes of interest include:

Food Sustainability

- Reducing food waste.
- Sustainable choices (local, seasonal, organic, minimally processed foods).
- Adherence to sustainable dietary patterns as Mediterranean diet